

CORRELATES OF MENTAL HEALTH TRAITS AND EXPOSURE TO SOCIAL MEDIA COMEDY SKITS AMONG NIGERIAN NETIZENS

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Abstract: *Mental health has gained increased global attention as a subject of concern in recent years. This research is focusing on traits that lead to emotional enhancement. Comedy is a genre of dramatic art that explores humour to initiate laughter amongst the audience, especially the short skits. There are studies that have established that there exists a relationship between mental health and comedy skit. With the rapid progression of social media, comedy skits have provided a supplementary or alternative means of therapy or means of fulfilling entertainment gratification among the audience. This study investigated mental health traits of Nigerian Netizens who are exposed to social media comedy skits. The study was anchored on Media System Dependency theory. The study adopted descriptive survey research design and a sample of 380 respondents bases on simple random sampling technique across digital media platforms. The study employed a self-designed structured questionnaire administered through Google form for data gathering. The data were coded and analysed using statistical package for social science (SPSS) with descriptive inferential statistics. The study revealed that Netizens were minimally exposed to social media comedy skits with the weighted mean score of 2.77 and standard deviation of 1.11, including a strong positive emotional stability, 347 (91.3%), resilience 294(77.4%), self-esteem, 223 respondents (58.7%), and environmental engagement 356(93.7%) among viewers with (Mean=3.22; SD=0.48). The study recommends that Netizens especially both youth, elderly, clergies and other religious leaders should consider comedy skits as alternative means of relaxation and therapy as it will positively enhance individuals' mental health.*

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Introduction

Mental health has gained increased attention as it became subject of concern in recent years, with most initiatives focused on attempts to develop culturally relevant interventions that can be deployed to improve mental health services and the traits¹. Despite some positive intervention and improvements in the world, mental health problems is still on the high side. Mental health has experienced paradigm shift toward a more holistic and positive perspective of the concept². However, mental well-being can be unclear at times, as it may or may not indicate the absence of mental illness or distress¹. Mental well-being has to do with the state of mind or total emotional and intellectual response of an individual to external reality³.

It is important to understand that mental health focuses on well-being which has to do with positive psychology school of thought that assists individual in the continuous maintenance of mental status with deep concern on individual motivation of life, good inner feelings and decent social adaptation. These promote healthy status and serene environment where individuals can live and contribute to the development of the society³. Mental health is a fundamental component of overall health, it encompasses more than just the absence of illness. Mental health is complicated, complex and intertwined with physical health and behaviour². 'Health is

wealth' as said by scholars, including some media channels and as such it is important for individual consciousness of health status and management in order to secure a balanced mental health, improve one's personality and prolong life span¹. A healthy state will go a long way in improving individual work productivity and effective contribution to the environment that one belongs. However, individual personality mostly demonstrates and communicates the level of mental health wellness, status, and traits¹. Health related information such as mental health and awareness have been top-notch discussion through various media channels like television, radio, print media and the new media².

Health can be referred to as the science and act of preventing disease, prolonging life, and promoting health through the combined efforts of the media and choices of society, organisations, and communities of an individual². Health is a state of the complete emotional, mental, and physical well-being of an individual as good health is centred on handling stress and living a longer more active life. Mental and physical health are undoubtedly the two major concerns of the health sector³. Study revealed that World Health Organization (WHO) revealed that Nigeria has one of the worst health indicators in Africa, which makes it difficult to achieve the SDGs goal. As the country experiences rapid

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growth in population, African countries face development challenges that are blamed on weak socio-economic conditions that bedevil the continent.

Netizens is a combination of the internet and citizen. It is an English term otherwise referred to as "citizen of the net" or "net citizen". The term describes a person who is actively involved in online community interaction and active engagement to improve internet communication¹⁹.

Objectives

This paper investigated two objectives:

- i. ascertain the level of exposure of Nigerian Netizens to social media comedy skits;
- ii. Identify mental health traits of Nigeria Netizens who are exposed to social media comedy skits.

Media, Mental Health and Health Communication

One of the functions of development communication or medical communication is advocacy, set up to campaign for health friendly regulation. The American Public Health Association (APHA) explains that media advocacy is used to promote a subject and influence social change by providing management tips. The mass media can advocate for positive change in health sector by educating the public through various channels causing a change of mind-set and awareness on some health issues, and influence friendly health

policies². The term 'mental health' is concerned with wellness rather than illness and is not merely the absence of a mental health condition⁴. Mental health can fluctuate with different phases of mental illnesses, which often involve deteriorations and reductions within a period of time while the frequency and duration may influence variation in mental well-being³.

The media has consistently strengthened the act of communication through diverse mediums such as television, radio, print and new media with arrays of contents such as news, music video, film, programme presentation and dramatic art including comedy skit. This is responding to a world, which is changing rapidly through the efforts of skilled media professionals and media innovation in the shadow of digital technology. Studies have revealed that content viewed through the media contributes to individual emotion and physical life style, as a result of exposure to various media content, certain personality trait is expected to be exhibited by the viewers after each encounter.

Mental health referred to a state of mind characterized by emotional well-being, good behavioural adjustment, relative freedom from anxiety and disabling symptoms, it also include the capacity to establish constructive relationships with people and society and as well cope with the ordinary demands and stresses of life¹.

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Correlates of Mental Health Traits, Comedy Skits and Wellbeing

Mental health is the condition of total well-being that makes individuals reach their full potential and allows people to deal effectively with stress, work efficiently, and contribute to the environment to which one belongs. Studies affirmed that there is a link between personality traits and mental health⁵. A related study also opined that mental health is regarded as the status of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realise personal abilities, learn well, work effectively, and contribute to the environment where one belongs⁵.

Studies have revealed that an alteration in mental health status does not mean that one has a mental illness as everybody is prone to display certain level of irregular action and behaviour at a particular time². Mental health is the totality of health well-being which can be great, poor, or somewhere in the middle². Mental health can fluctuate with different phases of mental illnesses, which often involve deteriorations and reductions within a period of time while the frequency and duration of may influence the variation in mental well-being¹. A related study stated that an imbalance in mental health can occur due to stress, burnout, grief, mental exhaustion, or physical fatigue that may cause challenges related to mood switch, sleep, and appetite but does not mean

that such action fit in criteria of having a mental health illness⁵.

African communities are now experiencing difficulties related to mental health. However, many members of the society are not sympathetic with people with mental illness. The study further stressed that a lot of issues can trigger mental illness. Mental health traits can also be related to categories of stress-related issues such as economic stress, social stress, educational stress or hereditary factors that can be attributed to war experience, spiritual factors, and aggression which might prompt humans to illicit sexual behaviour, to mention a few⁸. To this effect, there is a need for understanding and awareness among the people as one of the ways of addressing mental health

Comedy in literature is stories that can take dynamic forms as it does in other performances, including farce, satire, dark comedy, high comedy, and low comedy. The definition of the genre comedy is purposefully broad to encapsulate different dimensions that may be taken to make people laugh. While comedy and tragedy are imagined in opposition, comedies also have serious moments, and tragedies frequently employ moments of comic relief¹²

Extensive laughter offers physical benefits and can help to sleep better and improve immunity. A small-scale study in a hospital engaged in a 40-minute laughter therapy sessions twice a

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week for four weeks revealed that there was an increase in sleep quality and improved feelings of depression among study population.

Other studies suggested that media channels such as television, radio, and new media can be used to deploy information by adding mental health issues in the public discourse and calling

for action²². These modern means of communication prompted a technologically negotiated means to reach out or disseminate information that naturally flows to all manner of persons regardless of their place of abode, class, political, social, or religious orientations, and persuasions.

Level of Exposure of Nigerian Netizens to Social Media Comedy Skits

S/N	Items	HE (%)	ME (%)	VLE (%)	NE (%)	M	S.D	Remark
Nigeria Social Media Comedy Skits								
1	WhatsApp	129 (33.9)	82 (21.6)	72 (18.9)	97 (25.5)	2.64	1.19	Minimally Exposed
2	TikTok	274 (72.1)	60 (15.8)	24 (6.3)	22 (5.8)	3.54	0.85	Highly Exposed
3	YouTube	180 (47.4)	97 (25.5)	45 (11.3)	58 (15.3)	3.05	1.10	Minimally Exposed
4	Facebook	91 (23.9)	86 (22.6)	47 (12.4)	156 (41.1)	2.30	1.23	Very Low Exposure
5	Twitter	0 (0)	123 (32.4)	100 (26.3)	157 (41.3)	1.91	0.85	Very Low Exposure
Following Nigeria Comedy Skit Makers on Social Media Pages								
6	WhatsApp	112 (29.5)	96 (25.3)	63 (16.6)	109 (28.7)	2.56	1.19	Minimally Exposed
7	TikTok	259 (68.2)	58 (15.3)	31 (8.2)	32 (8.4)	3.43	0.96	Minimally Exposed
8	YouTube	169 (44.5)	91 (23.9)	57 (15)	63 (16.6)	2.96	1.12	Minimally Exposed
9	Facebook	96 (25.3)	84 (22.1)	50 (13.2)	150 (39.5)	2.33	1.23	Very Low Exposure
10	Twitter	70 (18.4)	76 (20)	77 (20.3)	157 (41.3)	2.16	1.15	Very Low Exposure
Eagerly Viewing Nigeria Comedy Skits on Social Media Platforms								
11	WhatsApp	123	96	73	88	2.67	1.16	Minimally

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		(32.4)	(25.3)	(19.2)	(23.2)			Exposed
12	TikTok	274	51	30	25	3.51	0.90	Highly
		(72.1)	(13.4)	(7.9)	(6.6)			Exposed
13	YouTube	160	107	52	61	2.96	1.10	Minimally
		(42.1)	(28.2)	(13.7)	(16.1)			Exposed
14	Facebook	98	87	55	140	2.38	1.22	Very Low
		(25.8)	(22.9)	(14.5)	(36.8)			Exposure
15	Twitter	78	69	79	154	2.19	1.17	Very Low
		(20.5)	(18.2)	(20.8)	(40.5)			Exposure
Weighted Mean = 2.77; S.D = 1.11; Overall Decision = Minimally Exposed								

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2025

KEY: Highly Exposed (HE) =4, Minimally Exposed (ME)= 3, Very Low Exposure (VLE)= 2, Not Exposed (NE) = 1, SD = Standard Deviation, M= Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 0.000-1.499 = Not Exposed (NE); 1.500-2.499 = Very Low Exposure (VLE); 2.500-3.499 =Minimally Exposed (ME); 3.500 to 4.500= Highly Exposed (HE).

The table presents data on the level of exposure of Nigerian netizens to social media comedy skits across different platforms and forms of engagement, using a rating scale ranging from highly exposed (HE) to not exposed (NE). The analysis covers netizens’ exposure to comedy skits, their interest in following comedy skit makers, and their eagerness to view skits on platforms such as WhatsApp, TikTok, YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter. Exposure through WhatsApp shows that 129 respondents (33.9%) reported high exposure, while 82 respondents

(21.6%) indicated moderate exposure. Meanwhile, 72 respondents (18.9%) reported very low exposure and 97 (25.5%) stated they were not exposed. The resulting mean score of 2.64 (S.D. = 1.19) classifies WhatsApp as a minimally exposed platform for comedy skits viewing. TikTok stands out as the platform with the highest exposure level, with 274 respondents (72.1%) indicating high exposure and 60 (15.8%) moderate exposure. Only 24 respondents (6.3%) were Very Low and 22 (5.8%) Not Exposed. The mean score of 3.54 (S.D. = 0.85) places TikTok in the highly exposed category.

YouTube also recorded substantial exposure, with 180 respondents (47.4%) reporting high exposure and 97 (25.5%) moderate exposure, while 45 (11.3%) were very low and 58 (15.3%) not exposed. The mean score of 3.05 (S.D. = 1.10) indicates YouTube was minimally exposed. On Facebook, only 91 respondents (23.9%) were highly exposed and 86 (22.6%)

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moderately exposed. However, 156 respondents (41.1%) were not exposed, resulting in a low mean score of 2.30 (S.D. = 1.23), thus placing Facebook in the very low exposure category. Twitter received the lowest level of exposure, with no respondent reporting high exposure. A total of 123 respondents (32.4%) indicated Moderate Exposure, 100 (26.3%) very low, and 157 (41.3%) not exposed. The mean score of 1.91 (S.D. = 0.85) places Twitter firmly in the *Very Low Exposure* category.

Regarding following Nigerian comedy skit makers on social media, WhatsApp had 112 respondents (29.5%) indicating high exposure and 96 (25.3%) moderate exposure. A total of 109 respondents (28.7%) reported no exposure, resulting in a mean score of 2.56 (S.D. = 1.19), classifying WhatsApp as minimally exposed. TikTok maintained a strong showing, with 259 respondents (68.2%) highly exposed and 58 (15.3%) moderately exposed. Only 32 (8.4%) were not exposed, leading to a mean score of 3.43 (S.D. = 0.96), still falling under the minimally exposed category due to threshold limits. On YouTube, 169 respondents (44.5%) were highly exposed and 91 (23.9%) moderately exposed, while 63 (16.6%) were not exposed. The mean score of 2.96 (S.D. = 1.12) also indicates minimal exposure. Facebook, however, had only 96 respondents (25.3%) as highly exposed and 150 (39.5%) not exposed, resulting in a mean of 2.33 (S.D. = 1.23),

categorized as very low exposure. Twitter remained the least engaged platform, with just 70 respondents (18.4%) reporting high exposure and 157 (41.3%) not exposed, yielding a mean of 2.16 (S.D. = 1.15), reflecting very low exposure.

In terms of eagerness to view comedy skits, WhatsApp recorded 123 respondents (32.4%) as highly exposed and 96 (25.3%) as moderately exposed, while 88 respondents (23.2%) reported no exposure. The mean score of 2.67 (S.D. = 1.16) indicates minimal exposure. TikTok once again led with 274 respondents (72.1%) highly exposed and only 25 (6.6%) not exposed. With a mean score of 3.51 (S.D. = 0.90), it is the only platform classified as highly exposed in this category. YouTube was also fairly strong, with 160 respondents (42.1%) reporting high exposure and a mean of 2.96 (S.D. = 1.10), placing it within minimal exposure. Facebook and Twitter were again the weakest platforms, with Facebook scoring a mean of 2.38 (S.D. = 1.22) and Twitter 2.19 (S.D. = 1.17), both falling under very low exposure.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 2.77 and standard deviation of 1.11 suggest that Nigerian netizens are minimally exposed to comedy skits through social media platforms ($x = 2.77$; $SD = 1.11$). TikTok clearly emerged as the most dominant and consistent platform for comedy content across all forms of engagement, while

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Facebook and Twitter consistently fall short in terms of exposure. These findings reaffirm the growing preference for visually engaging, short-form video content, with platforms like TikTok

and YouTube playing a leading role in shaping comedic entertainment consumption among Nigerian audiences.

Mental Health Traits of Nigerian Netizens that are exposed to Social Media Comedy Skit

S/N	Items	VTM (%)	TM (%)	PTM (%)	NTM (%)	M	S.Dev	Remark
Emotional Stability								
1	Enjoys feeling of calmness	12 (3.2)	347 (91.3)	21 (5.5)	0 (0)	2.98	0.29	True of Me
2	Enjoy stability of emotional thoughts	82 (21.6)	254 (66.8)	44 (11.6)	0 (0)	3.10	0.57	True of Me
3	Enjoy positive feeling	159 (41.8)	203 (53.4)	18 (4.7)	0 (0)	3.37	0.57	True of Me
Resilience								
4	easily cope with daily stress	17 (4.5)	294 (77.4)	69 (18.2)	0 (0)	2.86	0.46	True of Me
5	Ease of working effectively	123 (32.4)	227 (59.7)	30 (7.9)	0 (0)	3.24	0.59	True of Me
6	Ease of multi-task	256 (67.4)	116 (30.5)	8 (2.1)	0 (0)	3.65	0.52	Very of True Me (VTM)
Self Esteem								
7	Enjoy personal abilities	140 (36.8)	223 (58.7)	17 (4.5)	0 (0)	3.32	0.58	True of Me
8	Possess positive feelings about myself	88 (23.2)	292 (76.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.23	0.42	True of Me
9	Possess inner confidence about my abilities	173 (45.5)	188 (49.5)	19 (5.0)	0 (0)	3.41	0.58	True of Me
Environmental Socialization								
10	Finds it easy to contribute to my immediate environment.	24 (6.3)	356 (93.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.06	0.24	True of Me

Weighted Mean = 3.22; S.D = 0.48; Overall Decision = True of Me

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Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2025

KEY: Very of True Me (VTM) =4, True of Me (TM) = 3, Partially True of Me (PTM) = 2, Not True of Me (NTM) = 1, S.D = Standard Deviation, M= Mean

*****Threshold:** mean value of 0.000-1.499 = True of Me (NTM); 1.500-2.499 = Partially True of Me (PTM); 2.500-3.499 =, True of Me (NTM); 3.500 to 4.500= Very of True Me (VTM).

The table presents the mental health traits of Nigerian netizens who are exposed to social media comedy skits, using a rating scale ranging from "Very of True Me (VTM)" to "Not True of Me (NTM)". In terms of emotional stability, 347 respondents (91.3%) agreed that they enjoy a feeling of calmness, while 12 respondents (3.2%) strongly agreed, resulting in a mean score of 2.98 and a standard deviation of 0.29. The ability to enjoy stable emotional thoughts was supported by 254 respondents (66.8%) and 82 respondents (21.6%) who agreed and strongly agreed, respectively (mean = 3.10, S.D. = 0.57). Enjoyment of positive feelings also received strong affirmation, with 203 respondents (53.4%) agreeing and 159 (41.8%) strongly agreeing (mean = 3.37, S.D. = 0.57). Regarding resilience, the ability to cope with daily stress was affirmed by 294 respondents (77.4%) and 17 (4.5%) strongly agreeing (mean = 2.86, S.D. = 0.46). Effectiveness at work was acknowledged by 227

respondents (59.7%) who agreed and 123 (32.4%) who strongly agreed (mean = 3.24, S.D. = 0.59). Notably, the ability to multitask received the highest rating in this domain, with 256 respondents (67.4%) strongly agreeing and 116 (30.5%) agreeing (mean = 3.65, S.D. = 0.52), indicating it is "Very of True Me." In the domain of self-esteem, 223 respondents (58.7%) agreed and 140 (36.8%) strongly agreed that they enjoy their personal abilities (mean = 3.32, S.D. = 0.58). Feelings of self-worth were also reported by 292 respondents (76.8%) who agreed and 88 (23.2%) strongly agreed (mean = 3.23, S.D. = 0.42). Inner confidence in abilities was affirmed by 188 respondents (49.5%) who agreed and 173 (45.5%) who strongly agreed (mean = 3.41, S.D. = 0.58). For environmental socialization, 356 respondents (93.7%) agreed and 24 (6.3%) strongly agreed that they find it easy to contribute to their immediate environment (mean = 3.06, S.D. = 0.24). Overall, the weighted mean score of 3.22 and a standard deviation of 0.48 suggest a general agreement among respondents that social media comedy skits have a positive influence on their mental health traits (Mean=3.22; SD=0.48). The findings highlight a strong sense of emotional balance, resilience, self-worth, and environmental engagement among viewers.

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Conclusion

The study revealed that Netizens were minimally exposed to social media comedy skits on TikTok with the mean score of 3.54 (S.D. = 0.85) where the level of engagement to comedy skits is 274 respondents (72.1%), while following Nigerian comedy skit makers on TikTok with 259 respondents, while Netizens are also eager to view comedy skits on TikTok with 274 respondents (72.1%) highly exposed, as platforms such as TikTok and YouTube playing a leading role in shaping comedic entertainment consumption among Nigerian audiences. The study also highlighted a strong sense of emotional balance, resilience, self-worth, and environmental engagement among

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viewers with overall weighted mean score of 3.22 and a standard deviation of 0.48 suggest a general agreement among respondents that social media comedy skits have a positive influence on their mental health traits (Mean=3.22; SD=0.48)..

Recommendation

The study recommends that Nigeria netizens should increase and extend their social media comedy skits viewership to other platforms. Nigeria netizens should encourage other especially youth, elderly, clergies and other religious leaders to consider comedy skits as alternative means of relaxation and therapy as it will positively enhance individuals' mental health.

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